

WORKPLACE HARASSMENT, WORK–FAMILY CONFLICT, AND TURNOVER INTENTION AMONG WOMEN ENGINEERS IN PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Workplace harassment has emerged as a significant psychosocial challenge affecting women's participation and retention in male-dominated professions such as engineering. In Pakistan, where gender norms and organizational cultures often intersect to marginalize women in technical professions, empirical evidence on women engineers' workplace experiences remains limited. The present study examined the relationship between workplace harassment, work–family conflict, and turnover intention among women engineers in Pakistan. A quantitative cross-sectional survey design was employed. Data were collected from 85 women engineers working in academic and corporate engineering sectors using an online questionnaire. Workplace harassment and work–family conflict were measured using subscales of the Psychosocial Challenges of Women Engineers Scale, while turnover intention was assessed using the Turnover Intention Scale–Short Version (TIS-6). Pearson correlation, multiple regression analysis, and independent samples t-tests were conducted using SPSS. The results revealed that workplace harassment was positively associated with work–family conflict and turnover intention. Work–family conflict emerged as the strongest predictor of turnover intention. Additionally, women engineers working in corporate organizations reported significantly higher turnover intention compared to those working in academia. The findings highlight the importance of addressing workplace harassment and work–family conflict in order to improve employee well-being and retention of women engineers in male-dominated professions. The study provides important implications for organizational policies aimed at promoting gender-inclusive and supportive work environments.

Introduction

Women's presence in the field of engineering has grown worldwide over the past decade, but their retention rate in the field is a major concern. Although many women do enter engineering fields with strong academic preparation and technical competence, a rather high number of them leave the profession in the course of their careers. Research indicates that women's attrition from engineering is often linked to negative experiences at work,

unsupportive organizational climates, and a lack of opportunities for professional advancement as opposed to lack of ability or interest (Fouad et al., 2017; Fouad et al., 2012). These are especially acute in male-dominated fields of work where women often face gender stereotypes, discrimination and exclusion from professional networks.

Among the range of problems that women encounter when having to work in a professional setting, sexual harassment in the workplace has

become an important psychological source of stress. Workplace harassment is a unwelcoming behaviors that create a hostile, intimidating or offensive working environment and can include verbal hostility, exclusion, gender-based derogatory remarks and inappropriate interpersonal behavior. Psychological research has shown repeatedly that exposure to workplace harassment is linked to psychological distress, emotional exhaustion, reduced job satisfaction and impaired occupational functioning (Liang, 2024; McLaughlin et al., 2012). Persistent exposure to hostile behaviors in the workplace can have a negative impact on the professional involvement and overall well-being of the employees.

Engineering workplaces represent a particularly relevant context for examining workplace harassment. As a male-dominated historically profession, engineering is frequently associated with a hierarchically structured organizational system with masculine cultures at work (Sajadi et al., 2025). Previous research shows that women engineers often experience exclusion from professional interactions, questions about their competence as well as subconscious or more subtle forms of gender harassment (Fouad et al., 2017; Settles et al., 2006). Such experiences can have a detrimental effect on women's professional identity and lower occupational self-efficacy that may eventually lead to women's dissatisfaction with the profession and decision to exit engineering careers (Fouad et al., 2012). In developing countries such as Pakistan, workplace harassment may be further influenced by sociocultural norms, gender role expectations, and organizational practices. Although over the past few years, the number of women in Pakistan who are studying engineering has risen, the number of women who work in engineering is quite low. Women engineers who are working in technical and field-based environments may also face some additional challenges associated with gender stereotypes, workplace discrimination, and lack of institutional support. Recent qualitative research conducted in Pakistan also highlights that women engineers frequently experience psychological distress due to emotionally unsafe workplaces, gendered expectations, and work-family pressures (Asif et al., 2026).

Despite the introduction of different legal setups such as the Protection Against harassment of women at Workplace Act (2010), it has been suggested that workplace harassment persists due to underreporting, cultural barriers, and a lack of proper enforcement of organizational policies (Rahman et al., 2024; Naz et al., 2020). Exposure to workplace harassment may also contribute to general psychosocial problems such as work-family conflict and work turnover intention. Work-family conflict arises to the extent that the demands of work and family role become incompatible and it is difficult for individuals to manage responsibilities in both categories effectively (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985). Stressful work situations, such as ostracism and unbearable work environment, can amplify work-related pressure and cross into family territories. As a result, employees with high levels of work-family conflict have the potential to have negative attitudes towards their organizations and greater intentions to leave their jobs (Li et al., 2025).

Despite the growing body of international research on workplace harassment and employee turnover, limited studies have specifically examined these issues among women engineers, particularly in developing countries such as Pakistan. Most current studies are conducted in the general workplace population and not among the technical professions where gender imbalance and male-dominated workplace cultures may increase psychosocial issues. Furthermore, very little empirical research has examined the interaction of workplace harassment and work-family conflict towards women engineers in terms of their effects on turnover intentions. Therefore, the present study has aimed at discussing relationships between workplace harassment, work-family conflict, and work turnover tolerance among women engineers across Pakistan.

Literature Review

Workplace harassment has been widely examined in organizational psychology as a significant psychosocial stressor affecting employees' well-being and job-related outcomes. Workplace harassment refers to repeated, unwelcome behaviors that create a hostile, intimidating, or offensive work environment,

including verbal hostility, exclusion, humiliation, and gender-based derogatory remarks (McLaughlin et al., 2012). Research indicates that such experiences can have serious psychological and professional consequences for employees. Individuals exposed to workplace harassment often report increased stress, anxiety, emotional exhaustion, and decreased job satisfaction (Keenan et al., 2025; Liang, 2024).

A growing body of literature also highlights that workplace harassment is not merely an interpersonal problem but a structural issue embedded within organizational power dynamics. McLaughlin et al. (2012) demonstrated that harassment frequently occurs within hierarchical workplace structures where individuals in lower-power positions are more vulnerable to mistreatment. In male-dominated professions, these dynamics may be intensified due to gender imbalance and workplace cultures that normalize exclusionary behaviors.

One such occupation is engineering in which women can be at greater risk of being targeted by workplace harassment. Research on gender in female engineering has discovered that female engineers often experience gender discrimination, doubt of their ability, and a lack of professional connections (Fouad et al., 2017). Similar experiences have also been reported among women engineers in Pakistan, where emotional exhaustion, workplace insecurity, and work-family conflict contribute to psychological distress (Asif et al., 2026). These experiences in the work place may destroy the professional confidence of women and cause dissatisfaction in engineering careers (Fouad et al., 2012).

Likewise, the gender harassment studies indicate that aggressive behaviors of subtle nature such as sexist jokes and dismissive attitude are especially common at the workplaces dominated by males (Miner et al., 2012; Settles et al., 2006). Harassment in the work place and conflict between work and family. A work-family conflict is a type of inter-role conflict where the work and family roles are incompatible such that individuals find it hard to accomplish their duties in the two areas (Greenhaus and Beutell, 1985).

The stressors at workplace, including harassment, discrimination, and hostile work

environments can heighten the level of psychological strains and lead to problems in the balancing of both work and family commitments. Empirical research has also proven that negative experiences in the workplace can be transferred into personal life of employees. Workplace harassment may cause emotional depletion, stress, and a lack of psychological well-being, disrupt relationships and work responsibilities in the family. Because of this, the employees who are mistreated in the workplace tend to report greater work-family conflict (Liang, 2024). With employees who might already be already at work under heavy workloads and pressures to perform demanding tasks like in the engineering profession, the effect of workplace harassment might actually increase the strain of work-family.

Turnover intention is the intention of an employee to quit his or her organization. It is generally acknowledged that it is a significant predictor of withdrawal behavior of employees and organizational instability. The studies conducted in the past have always singled out workplace harassment as a large predictor of turnover intention.

In cases where employees are constantly harassed or subjected to unpleasant behavior at work place, they may develop negative attitude towards their organization and less organizational commitment. As explained in the Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1964), employees who feel unfair treatment or lack of respect by their organization may end up reciprocating by removing their psychological attachment and creating intentions to leave. Empirical research has revealed that the harms and mistreatment at the workplace are closely linked with the heightening turnover intention among employees (Folke & Rickne, 2025).

Workplace climate is important as it influences the choices of women in their career decision-making in engineering professions. It has been found that women engineers exposed to discrimination, exclusion, or harassment are prone to leave their organizations or even the engineering profession completely (Fouad et al., 2017; Fouad et al., 2012). Such results observe the significance of knowing how workplace harassment affects the career path and stay of women in technical disciplines.

Theoretical Framework

Resources Conservation (COR) theory is a valuable consideration of the impact of stressors at the workplace on the psychological health of the employees and the effects on their work. The COR theory suggests that people work to acquire, retain and defend the resources they deem valuable like emotional stability, psychological wellbeing and social support (Hobfoll, 1989). When threats and loss of these resources occur, people become stressed and strive to defend the resources that they still have. Workplace harassment is one of the key stressors that can potentially jeopardize the psychological and emotional resources of employees. Being subjected to offensive behaviors at the workplace may result in emotional exhaustion, stress, and diminished psychological health. To counter the constant loss of resources, the employees can seek to maintain their remaining resources by psychologically retreating in the workplace or might even think of quitting the organization. Consequently, COR theory offers a viable explanation to the antecedent of workplace harassment on the development of work-family conflict and turnover intention to the workplace.

The Social Exchange Theory also describes the reaction of the employees towards their treatment in the organizational settings. This theory states that employees and organization relationships are built on the reciprocal exchanges with the corresponding reaction of individuals to the positive or negative treatment (Blau, 1964). Once employees experience fairness, respect, and support at the workplace, chances are high that they will respond positively with good attitudes like commitment to the organization and job satisfaction. But in the event that people are treated negatively, whether through harassment, discrimination or hostility, they will also treat it back by lowering their commitment towards the organization and having intentions to leave.

In this view, workplace harassment is one of the forms of breaching the psychological exchange between the employees and their respective organizations which eventually may culminate into withdrawal behaviors like turnover intention. Work-family conflict is yet another theoretical point of view that can be used to

explain the interdependence between workplace experiences and career choice by employees. Work-family conflict takes place when work and family roles become conflicting, and individuals are unable to manage the tasks in both areas (Greenhaus and Beutell, 1985).

Harassment and stressful job experiences might also heighten work strain and emotional depletion that are likely to be transferred to the family. In a bid to balance between conflicting role demands, employees can develop more work-family conflict and dissatisfaction with work environment. As a result, workers with a high degree of work-family conflict can create a stronger motivation of quitting their respective organizations to create a balance between work and family duties.

Following the above theoretical views, workplace harassment can be defined as a major stressor at work place, which jeopardizes the psychological resources of the employees, and influences their attitude towards their organizations. Negative experiences in the workplace, which include being exposed to negative work environment practices, can aggravate work-family conflict and diminish the commitment of employees in their respective organizations hence leading to turnover intention. Thus, basing on the Conservation of Resources theory, Social Exchange Theory, and the work-family conflict perspectives, the current study suggests the following hypotheses.

Hypotheses

H1: Workplace harassment is positively associated with work-family conflict among women engineers in Pakistan.

H2: Workplace harassment significantly predicts turnover intention among women engineers in Pakistan.

H3: Work-family conflict significantly predicts turnover intention among women engineers in Pakistan.

H4: Women engineers working in academia and corporate sectors differ significantly in workplace harassment.

H5: Women engineers working in academia and corporate sectors differ significantly in turnover intention.

Workplace Harassment

Work-Family Conflict

Turnover Intention

Workplace Harassment → Turnover Intention

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the Study

Methodology

Research Design: The present study employed a quantitative, cross-sectional survey research design to examine workplace harassment as a key psychosocial challenge faced by women engineers in Pakistan. A cross-sectional design was considered appropriate as it allows the assessment of participants' experiences and perceptions at a single point in time and is commonly used in occupational and organizational research to study workplace-related phenomena.

Participants: The sample consisted of women engineers currently working in Pakistan. Participants were recruited from both field-based engineering roles and academic

engineering positions to ensure representation of diverse engineering work contexts. Women engineers from different engineering disciplines were included to capture a broad range of workplace experiences. A total of 85 women engineers participated in the study (N = 85). The mean age of participants was 29 years (M = 29, SD = 8.32). Data were collected through an online questionnaire distributed via Google Forms.

Participants were recruited using a non-probability purposive sampling technique. Eligibility criteria included holding an engineering degree and currently working in either academic or corporate engineering sectors in Pakistan.

Table 1

Demographic Characteristics of the Sample (N = 85)

Variables		f	Percent
Qualification	Undergraduate	23	27.1
	Graduate	26	30.6
	Postgraduate	36	42.4
Organization Type	Academia	50	58.8
	Corporate	35	41.2
Marital Status	Single	52	61.2
	Married	33	38.8

Measure: Workplace harassment and work-family conflict were assessed using the two subscales of Psychosocial Challenges of Women Engineers Scale developed by Asif et al. (2025). This scale was developed to explore the psychosocial challenges faced by women engineers in Pakistan and its items were finalized through expert evaluation using the Content Validity Index (CVI). The subscale was specifically designed to capture harassment-related experiences and work-family conflicts

relevant to women engineers working in male-dominated environments. Responses were recorded on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree), with higher scores indicating greater perceived workplace harassment and work-family conflict. The workplace harassment subscale consisted of five items ($\alpha = .82$). An example item is "Women engineers have to endure inappropriate jokes, unpleasant messages, or gossip and rumors at the workplace.". The work-family conflict

subscale consisted of ten items ($\alpha = .84$). Example items are “Women engineers are expected to handle multiple technical and administrative tasks simultaneously, which makes them feel burdened”; “Deadlines of engineering projects increase the mental stress of female engineers due to domestic responsibilities.”

Turnover intention was measured using the Turnover Intention Scale–Short Version (TIS-6) developed by Roodt Gert and Bothma Francois (2013). The scale is designed to assess employees’ intentions to leave their organization. The instrument consists of six items that capture employees’ thoughts and considerations regarding quitting their jobs. Responses were recorded on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (Never) to 5 (Always), with higher scores indicating stronger turnover intentions. The Turnover Intention Scale–Short Version has demonstrated good reliability and validity across different organizational contexts and has been widely used in organizational and occupational research.

Procedure

Data were collected using an online self-administered questionnaire. The survey link was shared with potential participants via professional networks, email, and social media platforms. Participants were provided with a

brief introduction outlining the purpose of the study, followed by informed consent information. Participation was voluntary, informed consent was obtained from all participants, and confidentiality of responses was ensured throughout the research process. No identifying information was collected. Participants were informed that they could withdraw from the study at any point without any consequences.

The study was conducted in accordance with established ethical guidelines for research involving human participants. Ethical approval was obtained from the institutional research ethics committee.

Results

The data were analyzed with the IBM - SPSS Version 23. Descriptive statistics were calculated for all the study variables. Pearson correlation analysis was performed in order to consider the relationship between workplace harassment, work-family conflict and turnover intention. Multiple regression analysis was carried out in order to test the predictive effects of the independent variable on turnover intention following recommended procedures of multivariate statistical analysis (Hair et al., 2019). Independent samples t-tests were also performed to test differences in organizational sector and marital status.

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics and Reliability of the Study Variables (N =85)

Scale	k	M	SD	α
WPH	05	16.91	3.65	.82
WFC	10	37.04	5.84	.84
TIS-Short	06	16.45	4.44	.78

Note. WPH = Workplace Harassment; WFC = Work-Family Conflict; TIS = Turnover Intention Scale.

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics and reliability coefficients of the study variables. The mean for workplace harassment was 16.91 (SD = 3.66) which showed a medium level of workplace harassment reported by the participants. The mean score on work-family conflict was 37.04 (SD = 5.85) which indicated that respondents reported moderate work-family

conflict. Similarly, the mean score among turnover intention was 16.45 (SD = 4.45) which shows that there are moderate intentions among participants to leave their job. Cronbach's alpha coefficients were used to establish satisfactory internal consistency of each of the scales: workplace harassment ($\alpha = .82$), work-family conflict ($\alpha = .84$) and turnover intention ($\alpha =$

.78). These values indicate that the measures that were used in the study were dependable.

Table 3
Pearson Correlations among Workplace Harassment, Work-Family Conflict, and Turnover Intention (N = 85)

Variables	1	2	3	M	SD
WPH	-	.63**	.26*	16.91	3.66
WFC		-	.35**	37.04	5.85
TIS			-	16.45	4.45

Note. WPH = Workplace Harassment; WFC = Work-Family Conflict; TIS = Turnover Intention Scale.
* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

Table 3 presents the results of Pearson correlation analysis among workplace harassment, work-family conflict, and turnover intention. The results revealed a strong positive relationship between workplace harassment and work-family conflict ($r = .627, p < .01$), indicating that higher levels of workplace harassment were associated with greater work-family conflict.

Workplace harassment also showed a significant positive relationship with turnover intention (r

$= .255, p < .05$), suggesting that women engineers who experienced higher levels of harassment were more likely to report intentions to leave their jobs. Additionally, work-family conflict was positively related to turnover intention ($r = .348, p < .01$), indicating that higher work-family conflict was associated with stronger intentions to leave the organization. Overall, these findings support the proposed relationships among the study variables.

Table 4
Regression Analysis Predicting Turnover Intention (N = 85)

Predictors	TIS		
	B	β	S.E
Constant	6.47		2.98
WPH	.08	.06	.16
WFC	.24	.31	.10
R ²	.12		

Note. WPH = Workplace Harassment; WFC = Work-Family Conflict; TIS = Turnover Intention Scale
* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

B = Unstandardized coefficient, β = Standardized coefficient

Table 4 presents the results of the linear regression analysis examining the predictive effects of workplace harassment and work-family conflict on turnover intention.

The overall regression model was significant ($R^2 = .12$), indicating that the predictors explained 12% of the variance in turnover intention. The results showed that work-family conflict significantly predicted turnover intention ($\beta =$

$.309$), suggesting that higher work-family conflict was associated with increased turnover intention. However, workplace harassment did not significantly predict turnover intention when work-family conflict was included in the model ($\beta = .062$). This suggests that the effect of workplace harassment on turnover intention may operate indirectly through work-family conflict.

Table 5

Independent Samples T-Test Comparing Single and Married Women Engineers on Workplace Harassment, Work-Family Conflict, and Turnover Intention (N =85)

Variables	Single (N = 52)		Married (N = 33)		t(83)	p	Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			
WPH	17.48	3.65	16.02	3.53	1.82	.73	0.41
WFC	37.00	5.86	37.11	5.91	-.09	.93	0.02
TIS	16.76	4.34	15.95	4.62	.82	.41	0.18

Note. WPH = Workplace Harassment; WFC = Work-Family Conflict; TIS = Turnover Intention Scale.

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

Table 5 presents the independent samples t-test results examining differences between single and married women engineers. The results indicated that there were no significant differences between single and married participants in terms of workplace harassment, work-family conflict, and turnover intention.

Although single women reported slightly higher mean scores for workplace harassment and turnover intention, these differences were not statistically significant. These findings suggest that marital status does not appear to substantially influence the experience of workplace harassment, work-family conflict, or turnover intention among women engineers.

Table 6

Independent Samples T-Test Comparing Academia and Corporate Sector Women Engineers on Workplace Harassment, Work-Family Conflict, and Turnover Intention (N =85)

Variables	Academia (N = 50)		Corporate (N = 35)		t(83)	p	Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			
WPH	16.61	3.53	17.34	3.83	-.90	.37	0.20
WFC	37.36	5.86	36.58	5.87	.60	.54	0.13
TIS	15.62	4.55	17.63	4.08	-2.08	.04	0.47

Note. WPH = Workplace Harassment; WFC = Work-Family Conflict; TIS = Turnover Intention Scale.

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

Table 6 presents the results comparing women engineers working in academia and corporate organizations. The results indicated that there were no significant differences between the two groups in workplace harassment and work-family conflict.

However, a significant difference was observed in turnover intention, with women engineers working in corporate organizations reporting higher turnover intention compared to those working in academia. The effect size for turnover intention (*Cohen's d* = 0.47) indicates a moderate difference between women engineers working in corporate organizations and those working in academia. This finding suggests that organizational context may play an important

role in influencing employees' intentions to leave their jobs.

Discussion

The current study aimed to examine the relations between workplace harassment, work-family conflict and turnover intention among women engineers of Pakistan. The findings bring important knowledge about the harassment that women experience in the male-dominated professional environment. These findings are consistent with previous qualitative evidence from Pakistan indicating that women engineers often experience emotional exhaustion, isolation, and work-family pressures within male-dominated workplaces (Asif et al., 2026). First, the results found that

both workplace harassment and work-family conflict had a significant positive relationship which supported the first hypothesis. This finding indicates that women engineers who experience harassment or hostile behavior in the workplace are more likely to have problems in balancing their professional and family lives. Workplace harassment may cause psychological stress, mental fatigue, and over-stress at work that may extend to the family lives of the employees. Such spillover effects have been highlighted in recent studies that show negative experiences in the work environment can worsen work-family conflict and lower the well-being of employees (Prakash et al., 2024; Wen et al., 2023).

Second, workplace harassment was positively associated with turnover intention. This finding suggests that women engineers who are being harassed will be more likely to consider leaving their jobs. Harassment undermines the sense of safety, respect, and support of the employees by the organization and may lead to loosening up of their commitment towards the organization. These results align with research indicating that being mistreated and harassed at the workplace are significant predictors of withdrawal behaviors at work, including the intention to leave the organization (Folke & Rickne, 2025). However, when the inclusion of both workplace harassment and work-family conflict was made in the regression analysis, work-family conflict was found to be the stronger predictor of turnover intention. This finding reveals the importance of work-family conflict in the context of explaining the decision to leave one's job. When the demands of work conflict with family obligations, individuals can suffer from role strain and psychological stress, which in turn can lead to decreased job satisfaction and lead people to have higher intentions to quit.

Recent studies have also found that work-family conflict is an important factor in deciding whether an employee intends to leave a company regardless of the domain of their work (Li et al., 2025). This pattern suggests that work-family conflict might be a potential mechanism that the harassment experienced in the workplace affects the turnover intentions of employees.

The results also showed differences in turnover intention due to the types of organizations. Women engineers working in the corporate organization have higher turnover intention as compared to those working in the academic organization. Corporate environments tend to be associated with heavier workloads, tight deadlines, and competitive performance standards, which may lead to higher work pressure and work-family conflict. These conditions may contribute to the higher intentions of the employees to leave their organizations.

In contrast, marital status did not have a significant effect on workplace harassment, work-family conflict or intention to leave. This suggests that it may not be that the psychosocial issues encountered by the women engineers are dependent on their marital status but rather on conditions of work and organizational environments. Both single and married women may experience the same type of professional stressors while working in engineering professions.

Overall, the findings of the study emphasize that workplace harassment and work-family conflict are important psychosocial factors that have an impact on the career experiences of women engineers. Addressing these issues is necessary to enhance the well-being of employees, decrease the turnover intention, and to contribute to gender inclusion in the engineering professions.

Table 7
Summary of the Hypotheses

Hypothesis	Result
H1	Supported
H2	Not supported in regression
H3	Supported
H4	Not supported
H5	Supported

Practical Implications

The results of this study have important implications for organizations and policymakers. First, organizations should create and strictly enforce anti-harassment policies to create safe and inclusive workplaces. Clear reporting mechanisms and management practices that support reporting can work to curb the prevalence and impact of workplace harassment. Second, organizations should adopt family-friendly policies such as flexible work arrangements, parental leave policies, and supportive work schedules. Such initiatives can be helpful for employees to better manage the demands of work and family life and lessen work-family conflict.

Third, organizations should foster inclusive workplace cultures that are supportive of gender equality and respect. Training programs around issues of gender sensitivity and workplace ethics can help reduce discriminatory behaviors and create healthier work environments.

Limitations and Future Research

Despite the contributions, there are a few limitations in the present study. First, because the study relied on self-reported measures, there is a possibility of response bias and common method variance. Future research may include some combination of multiple sources of data or a mixed-method approach, to obtain a more complete understanding of workplace experiences.

Second, the cross-sectional design of the research makes it difficult to establish causal conclusions with regard to the relations between the variables of the phenomenon, namely workplace harassment, work-family conflict and turnover intention. Future research may use longitudinal research designs to look at the influence of these variables on the career outcomes of employees over time.

Third, the sample size was relatively small and represented women engineers only in Pakistan, which may limit the generalizability of the results. Future research may involve larger and more diverse samples on industries and cultures. Future studies may also examine additional organizational factors such as leadership support, organizational justice, workplace inclusion, and mentoring opportunities that

may help reduce turnover intentions among women professionals in technical fields.

Conclusion

The present study examined the relationships among workplace harassment, work-family conflict, and turnover intention among women engineers in Pakistan. The findings indicate that workplace harassment is significantly associated with increased work-family conflict and higher turnover intention. When both predictors were considered simultaneously, work-family conflict emerged as the strongest predictor of turnover intention, suggesting that workplace harassment may indirectly influence employees' decisions to leave their organizations by intensifying work-family strain.

These findings highlight the importance of addressing psychosocial challenges within male-dominated professions such as engineering. Creating respectful and supportive workplace environments, implementing effective anti-harassment policies, and providing organizational support for work-life balance may help improve the retention and well-being of women engineers. Promoting inclusive organizational cultures is essential not only for reducing turnover but also for enhancing gender diversity and sustainability within engineering professions.

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